

Imágenes binarias

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Propiedades geométricas simples:

Area: la integral de la imagen en el caso continuo

Posición: Corresponde al centro de masa (\bar{x}, \bar{y})

Figure 3-2. The position of a region in a binary image can be defined by the center of area of the region. This is the center of mass of a thin sheet of material of the same shape.

Figure 3-8. A discrete binary image consists of individual picture cells, each of which may be either a zero or a one.

$$A = \iint_I b(x, y) dx dy,$$

$$\bar{x} \iint_I b(x, y) dx dy = \iint_I x b(x, y) dx dy,$$

$$\bar{y} \iint_I b(x, y) dx dy = \iint_I y b(x, y) dx dy,$$

$$A = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m b_{ij},$$

$$\bar{i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m i b_{ij}$$

$$\bar{j} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m j b_{ij}$$

$$A = \sum_{(r, c) \in R} 1$$

$$\bar{r} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} r$$

$$\bar{c} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} c$$

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Orientación: corresponde a la *dirección* de máxima elongación, se define como el eje de mínima varianza.

$$E = \iint_I r^2 b(x, y) dx dy, \quad \text{mínimo}$$

r es la distancia perpendicular desde (x, y) a la dirección de máxima elongación.

Figure 3-3. The orientation of a region in the image can be defined by the direction of the axis of least inertia. This is the axis about which the second moment of a thin sheet of material of the same shape is smallest.

Ecuación de la línea

$$x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho = 0$$

Ecuaciones paramétricas de los puntos en la línea

$$x_0 = -\rho \sin \theta + s \cos \theta \quad \text{and} \quad y_0 = +\rho \cos \theta + s \sin \theta,$$

s es la distancia a lo largo de la línea desde el punto más cercano al origen.

Coordenadas polares

Figure 3-4. Two parameters useful for identifying a particular line in the plane are its inclination θ relative to the x -axis, and its perpendicular distance ρ from the origin.

Figure 3-5. The perpendicular distance from a point (x, y) to a line can be found easily, once the closest point on the line, (x_0, y_0) , is identified.

Calcular la distancia de un punto a una recta implica buscar el punto mas cercano en la recta.

$$r^2 = (x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2.$$

Por sustitución de la definición paramétrica de la recta obtenemos

$$r^2 = (x^2 + y^2) + \rho^2 + 2\rho(x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta) - 2s(x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta) + s^2.$$

$$s = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta. \quad \text{Por minimización respecto de } s.$$

$$x - x_0 = + \sin \theta (x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho),$$

$$y - y_0 = - \cos \theta (x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho),$$

Por sustitución en las ecuaciones paramétricas de la recta

La distancia del punto (x, y) a la recta es $r^2 = (x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho)^2.$

Para obtener la dirección de máxima elongación se minimiza las distancias a ese eje

$$E = \iint_I (x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho)^2 b(x, y) dx dy.$$

Derivando respecto de ρ e igualando a cero

$$A(\bar{x} \sin \theta - \bar{y} \cos \theta + \rho) = 0, \quad \text{Donde } (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \text{ es el centro del area}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= x - \bar{x} & x \sin \theta - y \cos \theta + \rho &= x' \sin \theta - y' \cos \theta, \\ y' &= y - \bar{y}, \end{aligned}$$

Se reescribe la función en términos de las distancias al centroide

$$E = a \sin^2 \theta - b \sin \theta \cos \theta + c \cos^2 \theta,$$

Momentos de orden 2

$$a = \iint_{I'} (x')^2 b(x, y) dx' dy',$$

$$b = 2 \iint_{I'} (x' y') b(x, y) dx' dy',$$

$$c = \iint_{I''} (y')^2 b(x, y) dx' dy'.$$

$$E = \frac{1}{2}(a + c) - \frac{1}{2}(a - c) \cos 2\theta - \frac{1}{2}b \sin 2\theta.$$

$$\tan 2\theta = \frac{b}{a - c}, \quad \text{Derivando respecto de } \theta$$

$$\sin 2\theta = \pm \frac{b}{\sqrt{b^2 + (a - c)^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos 2\theta = \pm \frac{a - c}{\sqrt{b^2 + (a - c)^2}}.$$

Las **proyecciones** horizontales, verticales y diagonales tienen toda la información necesaria para calcular los momentos de orden cero, uno y dos de la imagen (objeto).

Figure 3-6. The projection of a region in the image onto a line that makes an angle θ with respect to the x -axis can be found by integrating along lines such as the one shown at L .

Figure 3-7. The horizontal, vertical, and diagonal projections contain all the information needed to compute the zeroth, first, and second moments of a region in the image. These moments, in turn, provide all of the information that we need to obtain the position and orientation of the region.

La proyección sobre una línea es la integral a lo largo de las líneas ortogonales a ella que atraviesan el objeto de interés (fig 3.6): θ ángulo de la línea de proyección, t distancia al origen de la intersección con la línea de integración, s distancia sobre la línea de integración.

$$p_{\theta}(t) = \int_L b(t \cos \theta - s \sin \theta, t \sin \theta + s \cos \theta) ds.$$

Proyección vertical, horizontal y diagonal

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 (\theta = 0), & (\theta = \pi/2) & (\theta = \pi/4), \\
 v(x) = \int_L b(x, y) dy, & h(y) = \int_L b(x, y) dx. & d(t) = \int b\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(t-s), \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(t+s)\right) ds.
 \end{array}$$

Momentos de orden cero, uno y dos a partir de las proyecciones

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 A = \int v(x) dx = \int h(y) dy. & \bar{x}A = \iint_I x b(x, y) dx dy = \int x v(x) dx & \iint_I y^2 dx dy = \int y^2 h(y) dy. \\
 \bar{y}A = \iint_I y b(x, y) dx dy = \int y h(y) dy. & & \iint_I x^2 dx dy = \int x^2 v(x) dx \\
 \iint_I xy b(x, y) dx dy = \int t^2 d(t) dt - \frac{1}{2} \int x^2 v(x) dx - \frac{1}{2} \int y^2 h(y) dy. & &
 \end{array}$$

$$P_V(c) = \#\{r | (r, c) \in R\}$$

$$P_H(r) = \#\{c | (r, c) \in R\}$$

$$P_D(d) = \#\{(r, c) \in R | r + c = d\}$$

$$P_E(e) = \#\{(r, c) \in R | r - c = e\}$$

Proyecciones verticales,
horizontales y diagonales en
notación discreta

$$A = \sum_{(r, c) \in R} 1 = \sum_r \sum_{\{c | (r, c) \in R\}} 1 = \sum_r P_H(r)$$

Area y rectangulo envolvente

$$r_{\min} = \min\{r | (r, c) \in R\} = \min\{r | P_H(r) \neq 0\}$$

$$c_{\min} = \min\{c | (r, c) \in R\} = \min\{c | P_V(c) \neq 0\}$$

$$r_{\max} = \max\{r | (r, c) \in R\} = \max\{r | P_H(r) \neq 0\}$$

$$c_{\max} = \max\{c | (r, c) \in R\} = \max\{c | P_V(c) \neq 0\}$$

Momentos de orden uno y dos

$$\bar{e} = \bar{r} - \bar{c}$$

$$\bar{d} = \bar{r} + \bar{c}$$

$$\bar{r} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} r = \frac{1}{A} \sum_r r P_H(r) \quad \bar{c} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} c = \frac{1}{A} \sum_c c P_V(c) \quad \bar{d} = \frac{1}{A} \sum d P_D(d) \quad \bar{e} = \frac{1}{A} \sum e P_E(e)$$

$$\mu_{rr} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} (r - \bar{r})^2 = \frac{1}{A} \sum_r (r - \bar{r})^2 P_H(r)$$

$$\mu_{rc} = \frac{\mu_{dd} - \mu_{rr} - \mu_{cc}}{2}$$

$$\mu_{cc} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{(r, c) \in R} (c - \bar{c})^2 = \frac{1}{A} \sum_c (c - \bar{c})^2 P_V(c)$$

$$\mu_{rc} = \frac{\mu_{rr} + \mu_{cc} - \mu_{ee}}{2}$$

$$\mu_{dd} = \frac{1}{A} \sum_d (d - \bar{d})^2 P_D(d)$$

$$\mu_{rc} = \frac{\mu_{dd} - \mu_{ee}}{4}$$

magenes binarias

Figure 2.27 Binary image segmented into regions on the basis of the segmentation of the initial vertical and horizontal projections. Also shown are the vertical and horizontal projections of each region.

Figure

Figure 2.28 Binary image segmented into regions on the basis of the segmentation of Fig. 2.27. Also shown are the vertical and horizontal projections of each region.

Segmentacion en componentes conectados basada en proyecciones o firmas

Figure 2.29 Diagonal projections P_D and P_E for each of the five image regions of Fig. 2.28. P_D is the diagonal projection taken 45° clockwise from the horizontal. P_E is the diagonal projection taken 135° clockwise from the horizontal.

imagenes binarias

Conectividad

Figure 4-1. When several regions occur in an image, the computations of position and orientation have to be carried out separately for each. Picture cells must be labeled so that those belonging to a particular region can be distinguished from the rest. To do this we need to decide which points belong to the same region. Here *A* is considered to be connected to *B* because we can find a continuous curve connecting the two that lies entirely in the black region. Clearly *A* is not connected to *C*, because no such curve can be found.

Detección de los objetos separados en la imagen como componentes conectados: conjuntos de pixels que son accesibles mediante una relación de adyacencia.

El análisis de conectividad puede aplicarse tanto a los pixels de los objetos (foreground) como a los del fondo (background).

Se distinguen distintos tipos de conectividad con propiedades distintas.

4-vecindario N_4 corresponde a los pixels adyacentes por filas y columnas.

8-vecindario N_8 corresponde a los pixels adyacentes por filas, columnas y diagonales.

or

Dos casos de 6-vecindario

Envolvencia: esta referida a la realización discreta de la propiedad de que una curva cerrada separa el espacio en dos regiones (Teorema de las curvas de Jordan).

Figure 4-2. A simple closed curve divides the plane into two simply connected regions.

0	1	0
1	0	1
0	1	0

B_1	O_1	B_1
O_2	B_2	O_3
B_1	O_4	B_1

B	O	B
O	B	O
B	O	B

Fondo y objeto etiquetado con 4-conectividad, 4 objetos y 2 fondos.

Fondo y objeto etiquetado con 8-conectividad, 1 objetos y 1 fondo.

Para obtener un etiquetado consistente del fondo y el objeto puede utilizarse 4-conectividad para el fondo y 8-conectividad para el objeto o viceversa. Las 6-conectividad permiten aplicar la misma conectividad al fondo y al objeto sin problemas de consistencia en el etiquetado.

Ilustración del problema de la envolvencia.

- a) imagen original
- b) detección con 4-con.
Fondo y objeto
- c) detección con 8-con.
idem
- d) detección con
conectividades
distintas en el fondo y
el objeto.

0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	0
0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	0	0

(a)

a	a	a	a	a
a	a	1	a	a
a	2	b	3	a
a	a	4	a	a
a	a	a	a	a

(b)

a	a	a	a	a
a	a	1	a	a
a	1	a	1	a
a	a	1	a	a
a	a	a	a	a

(c)

a	a	a	a	a
a	a	1	a	a
a	1	b	1	a
a	a	1	a	a
a	a	a	a	a

(d)

Figure 2.15 Phenomenon associated with using 4- and 8-adjacency in connected components analyses. Numeric labels are used for components of 1-pixels and letter labels for 0-pixels. (a) Binary image; (b) connected components labeling with 4-adjacency used for both 1-pixels and 0-pixels; (c) connected components labeling with 8-adjacency used for both 1-pixels and 0-pixels; and (d) connected components labeling with 8-adjacency used for 1-pixels and 4-adjacency used for 0-pixels.

```

procedure Classical
  "Initialize global equivalence table."
  EQTABLE := CREATE( );
  "Top-down pass 1"
  for L := 1 to NLines do
    "Initialize all labels on line L to zero."
    for P := 1 to NPIXELS do
      LABEL(L,P) := 0
    end for;
    "Process the line."
    for P := 1 to NPIXELS do
      if F(L,P) := 1 then
        begin
          A := NEIGHBORS((L,P));
          if ISEMPY(A)
            then M := NEWLABEL( );
          else M := MIN(LABELS(A));
          LABEL(L,P) := M;
          for X in LABELS(A) and X <> M
            ADD(X, M, EQTABLE)
          end for;
        end
      end for
    end for;
  "Find equivalence classes."
  EQCLASSES := Resolve(EQTABLE);
  for E in EQCLASSES
    EQLABEL(E) := min(LABELS(E))
  end for;
  "Top-down pass 2"
  for L := 1 to NLines do
    for P := 1 to NPIXELS do
      if I(L,P) = 1
        then LABEL(L,P) := EQLABEL(CLASS(LABEL(L,P)))
      end for
    end for
  end Classical

```

Algoritmo clásico de etiquetado que asigna etiquetas a los pixels en función de las de sus vecinos. Para resolver las ambigüedades se calcula la clausura transitiva sobre la matriz de adyacencia de las etiquetas generadas en el primer paso y se reetiquetan los pixels.

```

procedure RESOLVE(EQTABLE);
  list_of_components := nil;
  for each unmarked node N in EQTABLE
    current_component := DFS(N,EQTABLE);
    add_to_list(list_of_components,current_component)
  end for
end RESOLVE

```

Clausura transitiva,
 version
 Haralick&Shapiro

Version algebraica de la clausura transitiva

$$\mathbf{B}^+ = \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{BB} + \mathbf{BBB} + \dots + (\mathbf{B})^n$$

Algoritmo de Warsall (1962)

- Step 1. Set $j = 1$.
- Step 2. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, if $b(i, j) = 1$, then, for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, set $b(i, k) = b(i, k) + b(j, k)$.
- Step 3. Increment j by 1.
- Step 4. If $j \leq n$, go to Step 2; otherwise go to Step 5.
- Step 5. Stop. The result is \mathbf{B}^+ in place of \mathbf{B} .

(a)

Figure 2.18 Classical connected components labeling algorithm: Part (a) shows the initial binary image, and (b) the labeling after the first top-down pass of the algorithm. The equivalence classes found are 1: { 1,12,7,8,9,10,5 } and 2: { 2,3,4,6,11,13 }.

(b)

Figure 2.18 Continued.

propiedades aditivas: cumplen la propiedad aditiva de conjuntos

Figure 4-8. Binary images can be thought of as sets. We can combine two binary images by taking the union or intersection of these sets. The area of the union, $X \cup Y$, of two binary images plus the area of the intersection, $X \cap Y$, equals the sum of the areas of the original images X and Y .

La propiedad aditiva se ilustra por la suma del area de dos objetos en la imagen, que es igual a la suma de la union mas la de la interseccion. Propiedades que cumplen esta relación son aditivas y pueden calcularse de forma incremental

$$A(X) + A(Y) = A(X \cup Y) + A(X \cap Y),$$

Figure 4-7. The Euler number is the difference between the number of objects and the number of holes. The Euler number of this binary image is 4 since there are 7 objects and 3 holes.

Figure 4-6. Places on the edge of an image region can be detected by taking the logical exclusive-or of values in neighboring cells.

El perimetro se puede calcular por medio de conteo local que se consigue con las mascarar

La estimacion es $\sqrt{2}$ veces el valor correcto porque consideramos ángulos rectos.

Cálculo incremental del numero de Euler.

$$E(I \cup \Delta I) - E(I) = E(\Delta I) - E(I \cap \Delta I).$$

Se calcula sobre las tiras que se analizan sucesivamente en la dirección indicada.

En las tiras que presentan cambios $E(\Delta I) \neq E(I \cap \Delta I)$.

Figure 4-9. An image can be cut up into slices, each of which is simple to analyze. For quantities satisfying the additive set property, the value for the whole image can be computed from the values obtained for each of the slices. The computation can proceed incrementally, adding one new slice at a time.

upstream-facing convexities

$$\Delta E = E(\Delta I) - E(I \cap \Delta I) = 1 - 0 = +1,$$

upstream-facing concavities,

$$\Delta E = E(\Delta I) - E(I \cap \Delta I) = 1 - 2 = -1.$$

$$E = X - V$$

Mascaras de conteo local en dirección NW a SE

0	0	and	0	1
0	1		1	1

Figure 4-10. The interesting parts of image regions, as far as computation of the Euler number is concerned, are the convexities (X) and concavities (V) facing upstream.

Perimetro de una region sin agujeros: la secuencia de los pixeles en la frontera interior. Puede ser 4-con u 8-con.

$$P_4 = \{(r, c) \in R | N_8(r, c) - R \neq \emptyset\}$$

$$P_8 = \{(r, c) \in R | N_4(r, c) - R \neq \emptyset\}$$

$P = \langle (r_0, c_0), \dots, (r_{K-1}, c_{K-1}) \rangle$, La secuencia del perimetro ordenada
Sirve de base para el cálculo de la longitud del perímetro:

$$|P| = \#\{k | (r_{k+1}, c_{k+1}) \in N_4(r_k, c_k)\} + \sqrt{2} \#\{k | (r_{k+1}, c_{k+1}) \in N_8(r_k, c_k) - N_4(r_k, c_k)\}$$

$k + 1$ is computed modulo K .

$\|P\|^2/A$ Medida de la circularidad o compactación
En imágenes discretas es máximo para diamantes o rombos dependiendo de la forma de calcular el perímetro

$$\mu_R = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \|(r_k, c_k) - (\bar{r}, \bar{c})\|$$

$$\sigma_R^2 = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} [\|(r_k, c_k) - (\bar{r}, \bar{c})\| - \mu_R]^2$$

Media y varianza de la distancia del centro a la frontera.

$$\mu_R / \sigma_R$$

Es una medida de la circularidad, es similar para formas discretas y continuas y es independiente de orientación y area.

Puntos extremos

Table 3.1 Association of the name of the eight extremal points with their coordinate representation.

Name of Extremal Point	Coordinate Representation
Topmost left	(r_1, c_1)
Topmost right	(r_2, c_2)
Rightmost top	(r_3, c_3)
Rightmost bottom	(r_4, c_4)
Bottommost right	(r_5, c_5)
Bottommost left	(r_6, c_6)
Leftmost bottom	(r_7, c_7)
Leftmost top	(r_8, c_8)

Figure 3.1 The eight extremal points a region can have and the normally oriented bounding rectangle that encloses the region. The interior dotted lines pair together opposite sides.

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_1 = r_2 = rmin & & r_5 = r_6 = rmax \\
 c_1 = \min\{c | (rmin, c) \in R\} & & c_5 = \max\{c | (rmax, c) \in R\} \\
 c_2 = \max\{c | (rmin, c) \in R\} & & c_6 = \min\{c | (rmax, c) \in R\} \\
 r_3 = \min\{r | (r, cmax) \in R\} & & r_7 = \max\{r | (r, cmin) \in R\} \\
 r_4 = \max\{r | (r, cmax) \in R\} & & r_8 = \min\{r | (r, cmin) \in R\} \\
 c_3 = c_4 = cmax & & c_7 = c_8 = cmin
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 3.2 Association of the name of an extremal coordinate with its definition.

Name of Extremal Coordinate	Coordinate Representation and Definition
Topmost row	$rmin = \min\{r (r, c) \in R\}$
Bottommost row	$rmax = \max\{r (r, c) \in R\}$
Leftmost column	$cmin = \min\{c (r, c) \in R\}$
Rightmost column	$cmax = \max\{c (r, c) \in R\}$

Longitudes y orientaciones de los ejes entre puntos extremos

$$M_1 = \sqrt{(r_1 - r_5)^2 + (c_1 - c_5)^2} + Q(\phi_1)$$

$$M_2 = \sqrt{(r_2 - r_6)^2 + (c_2 - c_6)^2} + Q(\phi_2)$$

$$M_3 = \sqrt{(r_3 - r_7)^2 + (c_3 - c_7)^2} + Q(\phi_3)$$

$$M_4 = \sqrt{(r_4 - r_8)^2 + (c_4 - c_8)^2} + Q(\phi_4)$$

$$\phi_1 = \tan^{-1} \frac{r_1 - r_5}{-(c_1 - c_5)}$$

$$\phi_2 = \tan^{-1} \frac{r_2 - r_6}{-(c_2 - c_6)}$$

$$\phi_3 = \tan^{-1} \frac{r_3 - r_7}{-(c_3 - c_7)}$$

$$\phi_4 = \tan^{-1} \frac{r_4 - r_8}{-(c_4 - c_8)}$$

$$Q(\theta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{|\cos \theta|} & \text{if } |\theta| < 45^\circ \\ \frac{1}{|\sin \theta|} & \text{if } |\theta| > 45^\circ \end{cases}$$

Figure 3.4 Orientation convention for the axes. The orientation angle of an axis is measured counterclockwise from the column axis.

Figure 3.5 Diagram showing why the distance between two pixels must be increased if it is to count length going from the left edge of the left pixel to the right edge of the right pixel. Part (a) shows the distance between pixel centers; (b) shows the left edge to right edge distance. Each pixel must add a length that is the length of the hypotenuse of a right triangle having base 1/2. For $|\theta| < 45^\circ$, this length is $1/2 \cos \theta$ for each pixel.

Los ejes están emparejados: M_1 con M_3 y M_2 con M_4 .

El eje mayor es el más largo y el menor es su pareja. El eje menor es mayor que la anchura de la región.

En una región “línea” los ejes coinciden excepto el menor.

$$M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = \sqrt{(2 - 36)^2 + (7 - 5)^2} + 1.12 = 35.18$$

$$M_4 = \sqrt{(18 - 21)^2 + (7 - 5)^2} + 1.12 = 4.73$$

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \tan^{-1} \frac{-34}{-2} = -93.37^\circ$$

Figure 3.6 Calculation of the axis length and orientation of a linelike shape.

Orientación y longitud de un triángulo

$$M_{ij} = \sqrt{(r_i - r_j)^2 + (c_i - c_j)^2} + 1.12$$

Distancia entre puntos extremos

$k_1, k_2,$ and k_3 Indices que maximizan $M_{k_1 k_2} + M_{k_1 k_3}$.

$(r_{k_1}, c_{k_1}), (r_{k_2}, c_{k_2}),$ and (r_{k_3}, c_{k_3}) . Vertices del triángulo

$$L = (M_{k_1 k_2} + M_{k_1 k_3}) / 2,$$

Long. de los lados largos de un triángulo isósceles.

$$B = M_{k_2 k_3}$$

Base

$$h = \sqrt{L^2 - \left(\frac{B}{2}\right)^2}$$

altura

$$\phi_h = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{1}{2}(r_{k_2} + r_{k_3}) - r_{k_1}}{-[\frac{1}{2}(c_{k_2} + c_{k_3}) - c_{k_1}]}$$

Orientación (de la altura)

$$M_{13} = M_{23} = \sqrt{(6 - 26)^2 + (7 - 9)^2} + 1.12 = 21.22$$

$$M_{14} = M_{24} = \sqrt{(6 - 35)^2 + (7 - 9)^2} + 1.12 = 30.19$$

$$M_{15} = M_{25} = M_{16} = M_{26} = M_{17} = M_{27} = \sqrt{(6 - 36)^2 + (7 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 31.14$$

$$M_{18} = M_{28} = \sqrt{(6 - 21)^2 + (7 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 16.15$$

$$M_{34} = \sqrt{(26 - 35)^2 + (9 - 9)^2} + 1.12 = 10.12$$

$$M_{35} = M_{36} = M_{37} = \sqrt{(26 - 36)^2 + (9 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 11.56$$

$$M_{38} = \sqrt{(26 - 21)^2 + (9 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 6.95$$

$$M_{45} = M_{46} = M_{47} = \sqrt{(35 - 36)^2 + (9 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 4.28$$

$$M_{48} = \sqrt{(35 - 21)^2 + (9 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 15.44$$

$$M_{58} = M_{68} = M_{78} = \sqrt{(36 - 21)^2 + (6 - 6)^2} + 1.12 = 16.42$$

$$k_1 = 1, k_2 = 4, k_3 = 5$$

$$L = 30.67$$

$$B = 4.28$$

$$h = 30.60$$

$$\phi_h = \tan^{-1} \frac{\frac{1}{2}(35+36)-6}{-(\frac{1}{2}(9+6)-7)}$$

$$= \tan^{-1} \frac{29.5}{-3}$$

$$= 90.97^\circ$$

Orientación y dimensiones de un rectángulo

Figure 3.8 Geometry of the tilted rectangle. The diagram shows the relationship between the angular orientation θ_R and the angles of the axes joining opposite pairs of extremal points. Here (r_1, c_1) is the topmost vertex; (r_3, c_3) the rightmost vertex; (r_5, c_5) the bottommost vertex; and (r_7, c_7) the leftmost vertex.

En los rectangulos las diagonales son los ejes mayores y están, simult., emparejados.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= 180 + \theta_R + \alpha & \phi_2 &= 180 + \theta_R + \alpha \\ \phi_3 &= 180 + \theta_R - \alpha & \phi_4 &= 180 + \theta_R - \alpha \end{aligned}$$

Sea cual sea el eje mayor, la orientación del rectángulo es

$$\theta_R = \frac{\phi_1 + \phi_{m1}}{2} - 180$$

$$L = \frac{M_{(1)} + M_{m(1)}}{2} \cos \alpha$$

Longitud y anchura

$$W = \frac{M_{(1)} + M_{m(1)}}{2} \sin \alpha$$

$$\alpha = \min \left\{ \frac{|\phi_{(1)} - \phi_{m(1)}|}{2}, 180 - \frac{|\phi_1 - \phi_{m1}|}{2} \right\}$$

Orientación y dimensiones de un octaedro

$$L_1 = |c_1 - c_2| + 1$$

$$L_2 = \sqrt{(r_2 - r_3)^2 + (c_2 - c_3)^2} + Q(\theta_2)$$

$$L_3 = |r_3 - r_4| + 1$$

$$L_4 = \sqrt{(r_4 - r_5)^2 + (c_4 - c_5)^2} + Q(\theta_4)$$

$$L_5 = |c_5 - c_6| + 1$$

$$L_6 = \sqrt{(r_6 - r_7)^2 + (c_6 - c_7)^2} + Q(\theta_2)$$

$$L_7 = |r_7 - r_8| + 1$$

$$L_8 = \sqrt{(r_8 - r_1)^2 + (c_8 - c_1)^2} + Q(\theta_4)$$

Ejes y sus orientaciones

Side length	Extremal point	Axis length	Axis orientation
$L_1 = 3$	$(r_1, c_1) = (2, 13)$	$A_1: 5.295$	0°
$L_2 = 5.51$	$(r_2, c_2) = (2, 15)$	$A_2: 4.935$	-66.9°
$L_3 = 3$	$(r_3, c_3) = (6, 17)$	$A_3: 4.5$	90°
$L_4 = 10.55$	$(r_4, c_4) = (8, 17)$	$A_4: 10.575$	25.2°
$L_5 = 5$	$(r_5, c_5) = (13, 9)$		
$L_6 = 4.28$	$(r_6, c_6) = (13, 5)$		
$L_7 = 6$	$(r_7, c_7) = (10, 4)$		
$L_8 = 10.6$	$(r_8, c_8) = (5, 4)$		

Figure 3.10 Axes and their mates that arise from octagonal-shaped regions and their extremal points.

$$A_1 = \frac{(L_1 + L_5)}{2} \quad A_3 = \frac{(L_3 + L_7)}{2}$$

$$A_2 = \frac{(L_2 + L_6)}{2} \quad A_4 = \frac{(L_4 + L_8)}{2}$$

$$\theta_2 = \frac{1}{2A_2} \left[L_2 \tan^{-1} \frac{r_2 - r_3}{-(c_2 - c_3)} + L_6 \tan^{-1} \frac{r_7 - r_6}{-(c_7 - c_6)} \right]$$

$$\theta_4 = \frac{1}{2A_4} \left[L_4 \tan^{-1} \frac{r_4 - r_5}{-(c_4 - c_5)} + L_8 \tan^{-1} \frac{r_1 - r_8}{-(c_1 - c_8)} \right]$$